

Determination of Dissociation Constants of Some Amino Acids : Part II—by Spectrophotometric Method

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The authors have used Ernst and Menashi's method of ultraviolet spectrophotometry and have evaluated the pK_1 and pK_2 values of Cysteine (1.94, 8.82), Tryptophane (2.30, 9.44), Phenyl alanine (1.79, 9.16) and Tyrosine (2.18, 9.18) respectively. These compare favourably well with those found potentiometrically.

It is fairly well known that amino acids either absorb in the shorter wave length or long wave-length region, especially to a greater or lesser extent in the ultraviolet range. The main advantage of determining dissociation constants by spectrophotometric method over other methods, such as potentiometry or titrimetry, was that the optical measurements made at very low concentrations of the order of 10^{-4} mole/l were as accurate as made at higher concentrations and were most reliable.

Experimental

The amino acids chosen for this study namely Cysteine (α -amino β -mercapto propionic acid), Phenylalanine (α -amino β -phenyl propionic acid), Tryptophane (α -amino β -indole propionic acid) and Tyrosin (α -amino β [*p*-hydroxy phenyl] propionic acid) were obtained from British Drug House Ltd, Poole, England. The spectral results were recorded on Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer previously checked for wavelengths by didymium glass absorption peaks as also by checking λ_{max} of spec-pure solvents such as ethanol, acetone, methanol and chloroform. All results were obtained in an air-conditioned room (25°) with a thermostatic arrangement on silica cuvettes ($25^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$). Suitable wavelengths, in the region 200-300 nm, were so chosen that the difference between the extinction coefficients of the undissociated and charged species was large enough for the determination of dissociation constants by the method of Ernst and Menashi¹. For this, the absorption curves of the respective amino acids were traced in neutral, aqueous, 0.68 HClO₄, 0.036 NaOH and 0.55 N NaOH media. For comparison, the dissociation constants of the acids were determined on Leed and Northrup pH meter by titrating 50 ml of 0.01 M acid against 0.1 N KOH and 0.1 N HCl respectively for the two pK values of the amino acid.

Theoretical Background :

The theory given below is a combined contribution of Silverthorn and Curtis², Stearns and Wheland⁴ and Ernst and Menashi¹.

If the acid H_2A dissociated as

and

$$K_2 = \frac{h\gamma_2^2(A^{-2})}{(HA^{-1})} \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the dissociation constants, γ_1 , γ_2 are the activity coefficients and h is simply (H^+).

Lambert-Beer Law gives :

$$D = (H_2A)E_1 + (HA^{-1})E_2 + (A^{2-})E_3 \quad \dots (3)$$

where E_1 , E_2 , E_3 are the molar extinction coefficients for the species in brackets and by the same logic,

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 &= E_1 C & \vdots \\ D_2 &= E_2 C & \vdots \\ D_3 &= E_3 C & \vdots \end{aligned} \quad \dots (4)$$

where D = optical density. Ang⁵ has shown that the above equations can be cast into a form (by reasonable assumptions) :

$$\frac{1}{D_1 - D} = \frac{1}{D_1 - D_2} + \frac{h\gamma^2}{K_1(D_1 - D_2)} \quad \dots (5)$$

Hence the plot of $\frac{1}{(D_1 - D)}$ vs $h\gamma^2$ should give

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K_1 since the intercept gives the value of $1/D_1 - D_2$ automatically. The activity coefficient γ can be calculated on the lines of Davies⁶ and Butler^{6a} by using the expression :

$$-\log_{10} \gamma_{\pm} = 0.5 Z^2 \frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + \sqrt{I}} - 0.3I \quad \dots (6)$$

where $I = h + b \quad \dots (7)$

b being the stoichiometric concentration of NaOH added (as in the present case), $h = (H^+)$ and $I =$ ionic strength, Z being the charge.

Results and Discussion

For the purpose of final calculation of K_2 the expression used is a modification of expression (5) above and is written as :

$$\frac{1}{D_1 - D} = \frac{1}{D_2 - D_1} + \frac{h\gamma_2}{K_2(D_2 - D_1)} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{i.e.} = \frac{1}{D_2 - D_1} + \frac{kw\gamma_2}{K_2(D_2 - D_1)} f^2(OH^-) \quad \dots (9)$$

where K_2 is the second dissociation constant of the amino acid, kw , ionic product for H_2O (1.008×10^{-14}) and γ_2 is the activity coefficient of the species. The factor b , as defined above (expression 7), is used in evaluating (OH^-) as :

$$[OH^-] = b - \left[1 + \frac{D - D_1}{D_2 - D_1} \right] \times C \quad \dots (10)$$

where C is the concentration of amino acid.

It will be seen from the expression above that the values of K_1 and D_2 can be easily determined only if $h\gamma_1^2$ can be evaluated. Since h is defined by the expression :

$$h = a + \left[\frac{m(D - D_1)}{D - D_2} \right] \quad \dots (11)$$

where $a = (ClO_4)^-$ and is the stoichiometric concentration of $HClO_4$ added and $m = (H_2A) + (HA^-) + (A^{2-})$.. (12)

knowledge of D_2 is essential and for its evaluation from the graph, h is simply taken to be the concentration of $HClO_4$ as a first approximation.

It need not be stressed that in order to determine K_2 , known concentrations of NaOH are to be added to the amino acid solution. The present series of acids are specially chosen because they could form $5.55 \times 10^{-3} M$; $1.08 \times 10^{-2} M$; $5.64 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.50 \times 10^{-2} M$ aqueous solution with ease.

Although all amino acids absorb to a lesser or greater extent in uv region, the amino acids studied

by the present authors absorb⁷ in the given range of 220 to 300 nm. Beaven and Holiday¹⁰ have worked in this field extensively and have found that the molecular extinction coefficients (Em) of tryptophane, tyrosin in alkaline media are much higher than those in acidic ones. The trend followed in the present series (Table 1) is

TABLE 1—THE RELEVANT DATA OF λ_{max} (nm) AND Em VALUES OF THE AMINO ACIDS IN NEUTRAL, ALKALINE AND ACIDIC MEDIA

Amino Acid	λ_{max} in media (Em values in paranthesis)			
	H_2O	0.036N NaOH	0.55N NaOH	0.68N $HClO_4$
Tyrosine	273 (155.71)	279 (162.10)	281 (165.73)	275 (152.87)
Cysteine	250 (69.44)	254 (75.92)	258 (81.48)	250 (67.19)
DL Tryptophane	274 (193.2)	283 (202.1)	283 (206.9)	279 (184.2)
DL Phenylalanine	265 (74.66)	266 (78.12)	267 (79.29)	266 (72.91)

Em alkaline $\geq Em$ neutral $\geq Em$ acidic, unmistakably in all the acids studied which bears out the observation made by Beaven and Holiday⁸.

Strenstrom and Reinhard⁹ make an identical observation, specially in case of tyrosin, and assign the sensitive absorption in the alkaline medium¹ as due to the ionization of the phenolic group in this acid as :

Formageot and Schnek¹⁰ confirm this observation by stating that in the region 290.0 to 310 nm, the phenoxide ion of Tyrosin absorbs very strongly whereas the phenolic group of the acid reacts less strongly. The observation of the present authors in the case of tyrosin is, Em neutral $\sim 1.0 \times 10^3$ whereas Em alkaline $\sim 1.6 \times 10^3$ which holds good in other cases too, and lends excellent support to their observation.

The data given in Table 1 lists the absorption maxima and Em values for the amino acids studied in neutral, 0.036 N NaOH, 0.55 N NaOH and 0.68N $HClO_4$ media. The K_1 values have been listed in Table 2 and K_2 values are obtained from the expressions :

$$K_1 K_2 (D_1 - D) + K_1 h \gamma_2 (D_1 - D_2) + h^2 \gamma_1^2 \gamma_2 (D_1 - D) = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{and } K_2 = (D_1 - D_3) + h \gamma_2 (D_1 - D_2) = 0 \quad \dots (14)$$

TABLE 2— pK_1 AND pK_2 VALUES OF THE AUTHORS SPECTROPHOTOMETRICALLY AND POTENTIOMETRICALLY AND OTHER VALUES (a) AND (b)

Amino Acid	pK values	U. V. Spectrophotometry (Present work)		Potentiometry (Present work)		pK values by other workers (a) and (b)			
		pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1 (a)	pK_2 (a)	pK_1 (b)	pK_2 (b)
Cysteine		1.94	8.82	1.92	8.90	1.96	8.18	1.96	8.38
Tryptophane		2.30	9.44	2.42	9.42	2.38	9.39	2.20	9.55
Phenylalanine		1.79	9.16	1.81	9.26	1.83	9.13	2.04	9.31
Tyrosine		2.18	9.18	2.20	9.14	2.20	9.11	2.20	9.19

(a) Cohn and Edsall^{1,2} ;
 (b) A. Albert^{1,3}.

All these have been set out in Table 2 (as pK values) along with the standard potentiometric values of pK_1 and pK_2 with acidic and basic titration as obtained by authors and other workers in the field. Thus the present authors have usefully employed the method spelled out by Ernst and Menashi¹ though the initiation of this method by Benesch and Benesch^{1,1} is gratefully acknowledged by them.

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